

**Research Paper on 'New Brand Management Process
Model' and Research Frame Work**

For Patent Registration of the proposed BMP Model

Research Focus

**The Strategic Role of Brand Management in Building
Brands of Engineering SMEs in Pune**

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I. Abstract & Summary

In today's ever-increasing competitive markets, particularly with the internet revolution and e-commerce mode of trading, brand perception plays a significant role in selecting a preferred brand while making a purchase decision by the consumer.

A brand is the face of the business and its offered products or services. Brand identity is the visual component of a brand representing the core idea, the theme of the services/products it means. When comes Brand perception refers to the customer's opinion of the Brand. It summarizes how customers feel about the Brand, including every direct or indirect experience with the Brand. Every Brand represents a promise and the core quality that the Brand fulfils as functional, experiential, or self-expressive benefits. Also, it is a promise that differentiates itself from its competitors' brands. The Brand Promise is fulfilled at every touchpoint of the Brand. Brand touchpoints are any point where a customer interacts with the Brand or its products or services. It could be a simple telephonic conversation, website look, and feel, email communication, point of the purchase experience, interaction with marketing and sales personnel, or after-sales & service. Every interaction point reaffirms the brand promise and any shortfall at any level can affect brand perception.

Brand Perception is built over time and managed by the Brand management process. It is built on a marketing foundation and focuses on how the Brand can remain favourable to customers constantly. Brand management is creating, managing, and improving a brand. Brand Management has become one of the most critical aspects of business strategy.

Brand management is an integral part of holistic marketing. It is a specific area of marketing that uses special techniques to increase the perceived value of a brand. Branding and brand-based differentiation are powerful means for creating and sustaining a competitive advantage. Brand awareness, as one of the fundamental dimensions of brand equity, is often considered a prerequisite of consumers' buying decisions, as it represents the main factor for including a brand in the consideration process. Brand awareness can also influence consumers' perceived risk assessment and confidence in purchasing decisions due to familiarity with the Brand and its characteristics.

Research Problem & Need of the Research

The role of Brand Management when it comes to Small and Medium Enterprises, SMEs, is significantly underutilized and ignored. Based on various research findings, SMEs are not following the scientific process of Brand Positioning, Brand Promotion, and Brand Management compared to big corporate brands. SMEs tend to follow many initiatives related to these aspects based on impulse or superficial understanding of their markets, resulting in non-effectiveness in marketing and promotion efforts. Importance is given to setting up manufacturing infrastructure, distribution, required investments, quality control, etc. Brand Identity, Brand Promotion, or Brand Management processes are ignored or addressed with a narrow and superficial vision. In reality, the role of Brand Management is very dynamic in creating the desired brand image and sustaining the brand preference in customers' minds. Thus, the research findings will help establish the importance of the role of Brand Management for SMEs in the Engineering Sector.

II. Engineering SMEs of Pune

Due to increased investments in infrastructure development and industrial output, the Indian engineering sector has experienced unprecedented growth in recent years. Due to these, India has developed the capacity to meet the varied needs and demands of the industry. Engineering goods made in India are comparable in quality and price to those made in any other developed nation worldwide. Due to its close connections to numerous other industries, including power, steel, automotive, infrastructure, oil and gas, consumer durables, etc., this industry is crucial to the economy. The largest industrial manufacturing industry in India overall is the engineering sector. The two segments of this diverse industry, heavy engineering and light engineering, can be generally categorized (Figure 1.07). Most of the production activity is related to heavy engineering, which involves major players, primarily creates high-end products using advanced technology, and necessitates significant capital expenditure.

On the other hand, the light manufacturing sector employs medium to low-end technology. Entry barriers are low because they demand relatively less money and technology. The dominance of small, unorganized players with limited capacities and intense rivalry defines this market segment.

With domestic and foreign companies investing in the "Make in India" program and significantly affecting indigenization, SMEs are the foundation for current and future high-growth businesses. The chance to "Make in India" with no flaws and no impact is significant. The engineering group is anticipated to provide a business environment that enables and continuously aids SMEs in the manufacturing sector dedicated to distributing the appropriate product, the apt solution, the perfect quality, and outstanding service at a viable price in both domestic and international markets. The scenario mentioned above provides

SMEs with a wealth of opportunities to fuel their growth in numerous proportions when combined with the proper marketing and brand promotion strategies. Their distinctive brand positioning and constant brand management efforts will enable them to acquire the desired market share.

Pune, also called the “Queen of the Deccan,” is regarded as Maharashtra’s artistic hub. The district’s economic activities are dominated by agriculture, with industries and service areas following. Pune is growing to be an important manufacturing centre in India. The automobile and information technology (I.T.) sectors are well-known in Pune. In India, Pune City has the second-largest I.T. sector after Bangalore, which is growing quickly. Info-Tech Parks are being developed specifically for the growth of the I.T. industry. Major defence and research institutions like DRDO are also located in Pune. Companies in Pune produce, among other things, I.T. software, machine tools, engineering equipment, measuring equipment, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, consumer electronics, locomotives, agricultural products, and car parts. JCB India, Mahindra & Mahindra, Tata Motors, General Motors, John Deere, Cummins India, and Mercedes Benz India Ltd. Some significant businesses based in and around Pune include Alfa Laval, SKF Bearings, and Kirloskar Pneumatics.

Pune is regarded as one of the nation’s top SME centres. The USP of Industrial Pune is a first-generation business with enormous potential. However, there is a need to raise a lot of awareness about the general engineering business, particularly regarding government initiatives. The best way to communicate with people and inform them of the advantages of working in the broad engineering field is through social media. To spread information about different SME schemes, the government has established an SME cluster, a mechanism, and a single shared platform. This would provide both new start-ups and established businesses with an excellent starting point to use all the necessary information for their business’s advantage. They can readily approach this cluster of companies where professionals can mentor young business owners in the engineering sector. The wealthiest municipal corporation in India is Pimpri-Chinchwad Municipal Corporation, which has a sizable industrial base where many SMEs are situated. More than 10,000 of these SMEs significantly contribute to the engineering sector in Pune and Maharashtra. Turnover figures are challenging to estimate because MSMEs are not required to register under the MSME act. However, the Maharashtra economic survey will reveal Pune’s GDP increase.

Most of the Engineering company’s ownership structures in the Pune region are proprietorship and private limited companies. The yearly revenue range for private limited companies is between Rs10 and Rs100 million. Over the previous few years, private limited companies (33%), followed by proprietary businesses (37%), experienced the most significant revenue growth.

In this study and for the investigation, the author has only considered Small & Medium Enterprises. Engineering Group is a central point of contact for all the distributed and disorganized SMEs.

III. Literature Review Synopsis/Key Takeaways

Customers are the primary force in the modern digital economy. Those companies will succeed if they provide the most remarkable customer service, the most affordable products, and the most guaranteed positive experiences. The ordinary Brand will fade from prominence without a distinguishing feature.	(Kapferer, 2008)
SMEs have their unique approaches to marketing and Branding. SMEs engage in Branding to a lesser but still significant extent, focusing on the Branding of their products. In addition, it helps establish credibility for the company in the eyes of potential buyers.	(Ahonen, 2008)
Brand conceptualization is the first of four analytical areas that make up effective brand management in SMEs, Advertising methods, Establishing a name for a product, and Analysis and enhancement.	(Odoom, 2016)
“Branding, reputation building, and an acceptable organizational identity” are all components that must be proactively included by businesses to construct a strong brand identity. In addition, companies must convey and integrate their brand value propositions into all aspects of their identity and marketing communications with clients.	(Abimbola et al., 2007)
When it comes to internal brand management, there are a few key factors that provide a compass for the whole organization: the intended brand values, processes, and behaviours. Without this kind of internalization, it will be difficult for workers to provide the best experience possible for their customers.	(Ceridwyn King)
The success of SMEs is primarily affected by four brand-building efforts: “brand identities, integrated marketing communications, marketing programs, and secondary associations.”	(Odoom, 2016)
The predefined core principles serve as a guide for directing efforts and making important Brand decisions. Management of brands based on their values builds consumer confidence.	(Eggers et al., 2013)
Customer loyalty to a brand is the result of strategic positioning that emphasizes desirable characteristics such as “uniqueness,” “credibility,” “sustainability,” etc.	(Dr. Babaraju. K.Bhatt, 2014)
Compared to physical brand activations, online ones are more cost-effective, and it’s simple to track activation participants and evaluate results using campaign analytics.	(Gunawardane & K, 2020)
Marketing professionals are increasingly interested in clients’ emotional attachment to their brands rather than their financial value.	(Veloutsou & Guzman, 2017)

IV. Research Gap

Although many research studies are available on Brand identity, Brand Building, and Branding relations with marketing initiatives, few studies discuss brand management as a complete process model for engineering SMEs.

As advocated and described by J N Kapferer, the Brands are assets, and constantly they should be reinforced and nurtured by tangible innovations and intangible added values. He further recommends following ten fundamental principles of Brand Management;

1. Build your business value around the focused Brand, which projects a core idea that offers tangible benefits to the customer with a strong intangible element.
2. Develop all other sub-brands under the shadow of this focused Brand
3. Project yourself (The focused Brand) as a leader of the product/service category and be passionate about developing the standards of the category.
4. Maintain all the brands with a consistent flow of innovations based on the Brand positioning.
5. Establish direct linkage with the end customers with personalized associations.
6. Deliver personalized services.
7. To make your customers your Brand ambassadors or promoters, reward them for their active involvement and Brand engagement.
8. Encourage communities that share your values.
9. Establish a global identity for the Brands and their products.
10. Be ethical and project collective benefits of the Brand or Product instead of focusing on individual benefits.

Over the period, Brand managers have changed their Brand management strategies due to the technological revolutions and overall shift in marketing and brand promotion practices. It has become a more relational perspective from a mere transactional perspective. This shift has led to new methods, techniques, and tools to acquire desired brand equity.

As mentioned above, the ten fundamental principles of Brand Management advocated by J N Kapferer are appropriately applicable and relevant to Engineering SMEs. So, there is a need for in-depth Research to propose a definite road map for the Brand management process, keeping the Engineering SMEs focused on building their Brands along with achieving & sustaining their Brand value in today's competitive environment.

V. Proposed New Brand Management Process Model

Brand management is an essential part of integrated marketing. It is a subset of marketing that uses novel strategies to boost the customer valuation of the Brands. SMEs can build and maintain a competitive edge in their focused markets through Branding and brand-based differentiation. Building and maintaining brand worth requires a strategic approach to brand management. Creating a brand management strategy entails boosting brand associations, preserving or increasing brand recognition, and emphasizing brand quality. To attain the planned brand image for sustainable expansion, SMEs need to periodically assess their Brand management objectives and restructure their Brand communication strategies based on marketing insights.

As studied, in the context of Brand management, SMEs seem distinct because it is associated with entrepreneurial orientation, i.e., owner-manager. Therefore, the Brand is a result of their personality. Various Research suggested that brand management as practised by SMEs is different because it consists of a mental attitude and a more intuitive, experiential, and voluntary process, primarily determined by the personalities of the business's owners and top executives. Brand conceptualization is the first of four analytical areas that make up effective Brand management in SMEs, Advertising methods, Establishing a name for a product, and Analysis and enhancement. (TAVARES1, 2015)

Regarding advertising strategies, SMEs are more likely to employ crucial Brand Management practices than their less successful counterparts. It explains how Brand-focused SMEs can gain a competitive edge over their rivals by returning to "branding basics" like identifying and responding to customer needs and brand perceptions, developing brands that are both valuable and relevant, maintaining Brand consistency over time, clearly conveying Brand identity to stakeholders at all levels, and building a unified brand architecture. (Pierre Berthon, 2008) Marketing efforts for SMEs rely heavily on the owner's or manager's social network, which frequently shifts between personal and professional connections.

Networking becomes increasingly strategic and beneficial for SMEs when the owner/manager builds their professional network. (Audrey Gilmore 2001) The success of SMEs is most affected by four Brand-building efforts: "Brand identities, integrated marketing communications, marketing programs, and secondary associations." (Odoom, 2016)

Strategic brand management refers to establishing, assessing, and sustaining brand equity, visibility, and Influence to enhance revenue and achieve enduring organizational objectives. To enhance "brand perception, recognition, retention, value, and consumer loyalty," it is imperative for a company to establish a distinctive brand management approach. Effective brand management strategies can endow a corporation with a unique persona in the business domain. The act of defining a brand is crucial as it serves to demonstrate to consumers the unique qualities that distinguish it from others.

“The funnel Model” of the framework for SME managerial actions

As studied earlier, Krake (2005) presented the funnel model as a solution to address the inadequacy of a comprehensive conceptual framework for Branding in SMEs. He further posits that following the “funnel model”, the proprietor or manager formulates precise aims for brand building. It is assumed that the proprietor performs a dual function. Before the implementation of brand management, the proprietor makes decisions regarding the organizational framework of the enterprise. “The funnel model” graphically depicts the Influence of brand management on SMEs. The model serves as the defining framework for SME managerial actions. In terms of overall efficiency, the model emphasizes the significance of the organizational architecture and strategic positioning of brand management.

“Theoretical Model of Brand Management for SMEs.”

Victor Tavares (2015) proposed a theoretical model and conceptual framework for the Brand management of SMEs. The conceptual model suggested linking and clarifying the foundational elements like Brand Prerequisites, Leadership Orientation, Culture, and the actual Brand Management process implementation flow.

Along with Theoretical Model, Victor Tavares has also proposed the research framework as a “**Conceptual Framework for Researching Brand Management in SMEs.**” This conceptual framework, created from a holistic viewpoint, enables the determination of the variables (or pertinent differences to explore) that appear to be most significant, the relationships that are most likely to be significant, and, consequently, the information that should be gathered and analyzed, at least initially. It highlights aspects like **Brand Conceptions, Brand Organisation, Brand Strategies, Brand Building, and Brand assessment & development** for researching the crucial information required to measure the variables (or pertinent differences to explore) that appear to be most significant and the relationships that are most likely to be significant.

“The Brand Report Card.”

In 2000, Kevin Keller proposed “The Brand Report Card”, which was published in the esteemed Harvard Business Review. The study identifies ten common characteristics exhibited by the most successful global brands and generates a comprehensive analysis to aid managers in evaluating their Brand’s performance. The report card can highlight areas where one’s Brand is powerful, pinpoint areas that need improvement, and gain more understanding of a specific brand’s configuration. Building comparable report cards for rivals can provide a clearer picture of their advantages and disadvantages. The resulting scores can be added to understand the Brand’s advantages and weaknesses clearly.

New Brand Management Process Model, BMPM

After the in-depth study of various theoretical models, research framework structure and the brand report card, a new proposed **Brand Management Process Model, BMPM**, has been presented by the author. The model emphasizes the processes and managerial functions referring to every stage of Brand Management. The BMPM model and research framework are developed based on the “**Conceptual Framework for Researching Brand Management in SMEs.**” Presented by Victor Tavares (2015) with certain revisions.

As indicated previously, Brand management in SMEs looks distinct since it is related to entrepreneurial attitude, i.e., owner-manager. Therefore, Brand perception and image are a product of their personality. Numerous studies revealed that brand management, as conducted by SMEs, is distinct since it comprises a mental attitude and a more spontaneous, experimental, and voluntary approach, driven mainly by the personalities of the business’s founders and senior executives. Thus, there need to be numerous opportunities to build out a unique Brand positioning in their focused competitive marketplaces. Although Brand Management models proposed by Krake (2005) and Victor Tavares (2015) highlight the significance of organizational architecture, strategic positioning of brand management, foundational elements like Brand Prerequisites, Leadership Orientation, and Organisational Culture, they lack giving clarity in establishing the process guidelines for the process of achieving brand building involving the implementation of “Brand identity, Brand positioning, Brand promotion, and Brand performance” strategies.

With this new proposed Brand Management Process Model, the author sheds light on the recommended process flow of Brand Management in an SME environment. With the proposed framework of the new BMPM, the author intends to conduct field research within the Engineering SMEs to understand the existing awareness levels of the B.M. processes and how much they apply these measures to increase Brand awareness. The empirical findings will clarify the effectiveness of Brand Management practices for SMEs to counter their competition and build the desired Brand equity. It will also evaluate the gaps in the practices currently used by SMEs in their Brand building processes.

This conceptual **Brand Management Process Model, BMPM**, depicted in below identifies and suggests four crucial aspects; **Brand Creation, Brand Positioning, Brand Promotion and Brand Performance** in the context of a holistic Brand Management process to develop the desired Brand building in their focused markets. Each stage proposes the process flow and highlights the specific functions of Brand Management SMEs can refer to and address them thoroughly.

Brand Management Process Model, Source: Author

Research Frame Work & Research Elements. Source: Author

This framework aims to comprehend the constituent elements of each stage of the Process model of Brand Management and assess their relative significance in the context of Brand development;

Brand Identity and Brand Promise

1 - Brand Identity & Promise
Brand Identity & Brand Elements
Brand Values
Brand Promise & Brand Commitment
Marketing & Sales Promotion Collaterals
Website & Social Media Presence
Internal Branding & Employee Perception

Part 1 - Research Frame Work & Research Elements. Source: Author

1. “Brand Identity & Brand Promise”

"Brand Identity & Brand Promise" is the first phase of Brand Conception. It defines the foundation of the Brand's core ideology and communication platform with aspects like Brand Identity, Brand Personality, Brand Promise & Commitment, Brand Communication, and understanding of Brand Values, Mission and Vision by its internal stakeholders and company employees. It is an essential foundation which needs to be analyzed and formalized to build a unique Brand story which forms the basis of Brand Management and leads towards the second phase, i.e. Brand Positioning. It contributes substantially towards building the Brand and creates a unique personality for the Brand. If something goes wrong in this phase or gets decided without in-depth study, it can hamper the entire Brand building initiative negatively. Every company has to be very careful in defining all these standards since the Brand personality depends on this.

Brand Positioning Strategy

2 - Brand Positioning Strategy
Company Leadership & Life Cycle stage of the Brand
Market Geographics & Competitor Analysis
Brand Positioning Platform
Brand Building Strategy
Advertising & Sales Promotion Strategy
Content & Messaging Strategy

Part 2: Research Frame Work & Research Elements. Source: Author

2. “Brand Positioning Strategy.”

Brand Positioning Strategy is the second phase of the proposed new Brand Management Process Model. After establishing the Brand Identity, Brand Values, and Brand Promise as Brand prerequisites, SMEs need to work on their Brand Positioning Strategy for the focused markets to ensure the long-lasting success of their product or services. Brand positioning is a critical stage for researching & analyzing the markets in terms of the competitor landscape, market potential, product life cycle, etc. Brand Positioning is a roadmap for creating an exclusive and unique proposition amongst the crowded markets to stand out for the customers. Advertising, Sales Promotion, and Digital Marketing are the various tools one can apply to build their Brand and acquire desired market share. As part of the Brand building process, creating the Brand Positioning Strategy becomes a critical phase that defines the clear and constructive path to penetrate and build the markets.

Brand Promotion & Sales Promotion

3 - Brand & Sales Promotion
Campaign Objective
Focused Markets & Target Audience Profiling
Advertising & Promotion Plan with Media Mix & Budgets
Designing & Development of Branding & Sales Promotion Campaigns
Integrated Marketing & Sales Promotion Activities

Part 3 - Research Frame Work & Research Elements. Source: Author

3. Brand Promotion & Sales Promotion

Brand Promotion & Sales Promotion is the third phase of the proposed new Brand Management Process Model. After establishing the Brand Positioning Platform, Brand Building Strategy, Advertising, Sales Promotion, and Content & Messaging Strategies, SMEs need to work on their Brand Building Sales promotion campaigns within the focused markets to ensure the long-lasting success of their product or services. Brand building & Sales promotion is a critical stages for establishing the desired Brand awareness and Brand perception in the minds of focused customers. Analyzing and planning on Campaign objectives, Target Audience profiles, Advertising & Promotion media mix, and Designing campaigns and integrating them with the marketing initiatives is the roadmap for generating Sales volumes and Brand awareness.

Measuring & Interpreting Brand Performance
Campaign Analytics
Brand Equity Management System
Brand Experience & Brand Recognition
Customer Retention & Brand Loyalties
Revitalizing Brands
Reframing the Brand Communication

Part 4 - Research Frame Work & Research Elements. Source: Author

4. Measuring and Interpreting Brand Performance

Measuring & Interpreting Brand Performance is the fourth phase of the proposed new Brand Management Process Model. Brand performance refers to systematically evaluating the results of brand building and sales promotion initiatives. SMEs should assess the strengths and weaknesses of their Brand by monitoring essential performance indicators, including impressions, traffic, and engagement, and subsequently comparing them to their brand performance objectives. Brand Performance measures like Campaign analytics, Brand awareness, Brand Recognition and Brand Recall are the markers to identify Brand Success. Based on the performance metrics, SMEs can reframe Brand communication to offer a better Brand experience and increase Brand loyalties. By analyzing the level of Brand acceptance, companies can understand the life stage of the Brand and decide on the Brand communication policies for revitalizing Brand positioning.

V. Research Methodology, Framework & Brand Management Model

Considering the nature of the research data, which will mainly revolve around subjectivity and perception-based decision-making processes, the hybrid research methodology (Quantitative Qualitative & Case Study) approach will prove more effective for the proposed research. The focused subject of research deals with various business promoters and decision-makers with a mix of demographics. The flexibility of Quantitative and Qualitative aspects of the target audience will give the desired insights. Since the research will deal with subjectivity and perception-based decision-making processes, it will discover the underlying motives and desires using in-depth interviews.

Research Questionnaire

The research questionnaire is developed covering all the aspects of the independent variable projected above with the 5 Point Likert Scale and a one-to-one interview questionnaire.

VI. Questionnaire for Research According to the Proposed BMPM Model

1. Brand Identity & Brand Promise

Question Statements		7-Point Likert Scale						
Brand Identity & Positioning		No	Mostly No	Somewhat No	Neither No nor Yes	Somewhat Yes	Mostly Yes	Yes
1	The Brand Identity (Logo/Symbol) interprets the core idea and personality of the business.							
2	The Brand Logo has a tagline summarising the core benefit to the customer.							
3	The Brand is recognized for a specific set of values like Trustworthy, Quality, Reliability, fairness, Professional, Cost Effective, etc.							
4	The Brand has a specific promise to deliver the core value proposition, which is fulfilled.							
5	Company brochures, Product brochures, Emailers, Technical Catalogues, Presentations, etc., are professionally done, and it carries a very high & lasting impact.							
6	The company website is professionally done and carries a very high & lasting impact.							
7	The company website is frequently updated and covers all the information about your brand offerings.							
8	The SEO (Search Engine Optimization) is implemented consistently to have better search rankings on Google & other search portals.							
9	The company's social media pages exist and are updated consistently and professionally.							
10	The social media followers community represent the target audience of the business.							
11	The company's employees know the Brand Identity, Brand Promise, Brand Positioning, etc.							

2. Brand Positioning Strategy

Brand Positioning Strategy		No	Mostly No	Somewhat No	Neither No nor Yes	Somewhat Yes	Mostly Yes	Yes
12	The company leadership is dynamic, business development oriented & forward-looking.							
13	The Brand potential is fully explored in the targeted market.							
14	Competitor analysis is done consistently in the focused market.							
15	The Brand offers a unique set of benefits to its customers amongst the competitors in the focused markets.							
16	The Brand Building Strategy (tactics, promotion, media, P.R., etc.) is developed on the platform of the overall marketing plan.							
17	The Advertising & Sales Promotion (for products/services) Strategy is developed based on the Brand Building Strategy.							
18	The Content & Messaging Strategies are worked on keeping the Branding, Advertising & Sales Promotion objectives focused.							

3. Brand & Sales Promotion

Brand & Sales Promotion		No	Mostly No	Somewhat No	Neither No nor Yes	Somewhat Yes	Mostly Yes	Yes
19	We study and define the target audience, market characteristics and campaign objectives before developing the branding or promotion campaigns.							
20	We work on the Advertising & Promotion Plan with Media Mix & Budgets based on objectives before launching the campaign.							
21	We develop our campaigns (online & offline) professionally with detailed Analysis of the competitive campaigns running in the markets.							
22	We follow a structured and pre-planned schedule for implementing Branding & Sales Promotion Campaigns in a designated period.							
23	The marketing & promotion activities are integrated and implemented, complementing each other for effective outcomes.							

4. Measuring & Interpreting Brand Performance

Measuring & Interpreting Brand Performance		No	Mostly No	Somewhat No	Neither No or Yes	Somewhat Yes	Mostly Yes	Yes
23	We analyze campaign analytics for the reach and effectiveness of the outcome.							
24	We have a system/process to check and analyze the Brand Equity based on various Branding & promotion campaigns' effectiveness.							
25	We research and analyze the kind of Brand Experience end customers have.							
26	We research and analyze how much Brand Recognition and recall the brand commands amongst the competitive brands.							
27	The Brand commands customer retention and loyalty amongst the competitive brands within the focused markets.							
28	We work on rejuvenating the brand personality once it reaches its fullest potential.							
29	We re-launch the Brand with a new set of value propositions once it reaches its fullest potential with changing market dynamics and a competitive environment.							

VII. Conclusion

The data collected from the above questionnaire will give insights into the current practises of Brand building and Brand management exercised by SMEs. It will also highlight the gaps and shortcomings hampering the overall Brand building objectives to achieve desired business growth. The proposed new Brand Management Process Model Research Framework will address the following objectives;

- To discover the current Brand management practices used by SMEs.
- To understand how much Brand management influences strengthening the Brand value in the focused markets.
- To study the critical and influential aspects that differentiate the brands from their competition.
- To study the various initiatives commonly used by SMEs in Creating Brand Identity, Brand Promise, Brand Positioning, Brand Promotion, Marketing Initiatives, Content Marketing, Customer Perception & Preferences study, and Internal Branding.

- To propose a conceptual Process Model of Brand Management to Engineering SMEs, which will provide a recommended road map for business promoters to plan their marketing and brand promotion strategies for sustaining the business volumes consistently.

Research Outcome will offer the following Significant Benefits for Engineering SMEs;

- The research findings will present the recommended Brand Management processes to SMEs for defining the Brand identity, Brand positioning, and sustaining the Brand in the competitive landscape of their markets.
- The proposed new Brand Management Model will provide a recommended road map for business promoters to plan their marketing and brand promotion strategies to sustain business volumes consistently.

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